

ROTH Power System Model - Technical Documentation
Version 1.0 (December 2025)

Author: Michael Buchdahl Roth
Affiliation: Vassar College
Release Date: December 2025

Purpose

This document provides an overview, instructions, technical description - including a list of inputs and outputs - for Version 1.0 of the ROTH Power System Model.

Abstract

The ROTH power system model version 1.0 is open source, Excel-based, has an hourly time resolution, and can be used to quickly simulate a wide variety of small and large single-region power systems. This model is especially useful in modeling electricity islands, which can be a single building, a micro-grid, a city, state, region, country. The model requires the user to provide location specific hourly solar PV data from a 1 MW system, which can be downloaded using the National Renewable Energy Lab's PVWatts Calculator. The model user also needs to have hourly demand data. The model can be used to quickly evaluate clean energy scenarios and renewable portfolio standards. The model has adjustable inputs for the installed capacity of solar PV, nuclear, and storage size.

1. Model Structure and Overview

Notes	Model Explanation by Column
1	Column J is hourly solar PV generation from a 1 MW installation. Data available from NREL PVWatts Calculator.
2	Column M is for hourly total electricity system demand.
3	Column N is hourly demand after nuclear generation.
4	Column O is hourly generation from Solar PV.
5	Column P is the hourly demand left after generation from nuclear and solar PV.
6	Column Q displays a value for the extra solar PV generation that is above system demand.
7	Column R displays if the battery is charging or draining for each hour.
8	Columns T, U, & V model battery storage. Column T is charge in, Column U is stored electricity, Column V is charge out.
9	Column X displays natural gas generation, which is dispatched only if demand cannot be met from nuclear, PV, and storage.
10	Column Z displays curtailed solar PV generation, which occurs if there is excess solar PV and the battery is at capacity.

2. User Inputs

Steps	Setting up the Model: Yellow Cells Are Adjustable User Inputs
1	Enter hourly solar generation from a 1 MW installation in Column J. Location specific data are available from NREL's PVWatts Calculator.
2	Enter total system electricity demand in column M. The demand can be MW or MWh, since the resolution is hourly.
3	If your system has nuclear power, enter the installed nuclear power capacity and annual capacity factor in MW in the user inputs table.
4	You can enter the size of the solar PV generation, storage capacity, and storage round trip efficiency, in the user inputs table.

3. Model Outputs

Notes	Model Output: Light Blue Cells Are Model Outputs
1	The output table displays the total TWh of generation from each technology and solar PV curtailment.
2	The annual percentage of generation met by each technology is displayed in the output table.
3	You can now vary the size of the solar PV generation and storage capacity in the user inputs table until annual demand is met.
4	Solar PV capacity and storage size can be varied manually or using Excel's "Goal seek" function to achieve a specific target. To vary two inputs at once, such as solar PV size and storage, and view a specific output like percentage of generation met, use the Excel What-if Analysis "Data Tables" function.
5	Some system configurations will not be capable of meeting a renewable portfolio standard goal or clean energy standard.
6	There is an output cell that shows the max natural gas generation in MW, this is the minimum capacity required for the system to operate in each hour of the year.
7	There is an output cell displaying total annual solar PV generation from the system, before storage and curtailment. In version 1.0, the curtailment variable assumes that the storage round trip efficiency is meant to be set to 100%. If round trip efficiency is below 100%, then curtailment includes round trip efficiency losses from storage.
8	There are two cells displaying annual demand and annual generation. If the system is feasible, they are equal.

4. Assumptions

This model assumes that a power system is one region. The model assumes that anything not met by solar PV, nuclear generation, or storage discharging, is met by natural gas generation. For buildings or microgrids, the natural gas generation that meets all remaining demand can be viewed as electricity from the grid.

5. Limitations

This model only has three generation options. In future model versions, generation from additional technologies, such as wind turbines, will be added. Additionally, the curtailment and round trip efficiency calculations will be separated.

How to cite:

Roth, M. B. (2025). ROTH Power System Model – Technical Documentation (Version 1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17808838>

Website and Excel file:

<https://rothenergysystemmodel.godaddysites.com>